

PROBLEMS AND THEORITICAL TRANSLATION ISSUES OF TOURISM TERMS FROM ENGLISH INTO UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the field of terminology and its theoretical issues, in particular, terms related to tourism and their translation problems.

Tourism terms translation is a highly specialized discourse with its defining characteristics. The errors and strategies in translating tourism terms are under-researched in the tourism literature and similarly there is little discussion of tourism material in translation research. It is argued that for translations of tourism terms to enhance the tourist's experience, translations should not be literal but multidimensional i.e. culturally sensitive to their target audience and based on theories now available in translation studies. Thus, regardless of the accuracy of a translation, if the norms of the target community are overlooked it is a poor translation. The translation of information that tourist destinations provide to their visitors is an important factor in effective translation.

In the globalization era, people tend to travel more and to discover new places and cultures. On the other hand, tourist destinations seek to attract more and more tourists. That is why tourism terms play an important role in tourist and marketing industry and that is why there is a need to translate documents of tourist propaganda.

Newmark (1988, p.81) makes a distinction between translation methods and translation procedures by stating that translation methods relate to whole texts while translation procedures are used for sentences and the smaller units of language. He has categorized methods of translation into the following types:

- Word-for-word translation: in which the source language word order is preserved and the words translated singly by their most common meanings, out of context.
- Literal translation: in which the source language grammatical constructions are converted to their nearest TL equivalents, but the lexical words are again translated singly, out of context. Newmark (1988) argues that literal translation ranges from word for word translation to to collocation to collocation, to clause to clause, and finally to sentence to sentence translation. Venuti (2000) encourages translators to be accurate as they are not legitimized to change words that have one-to-one translations only because they think other translations sound better than the Strategies and Errors in Translating Tourism Brochures:

the case of EFL Learners 2769 original. Thus, under many circumstances, literal translation is considered an appropriate strategy by which a given audience is given basic information about the travel and tourism.

□ Faithful translation: it attempts to produce the precise contextual meaning of the original within the constraints of the target language grammatical structures.

□ Semantic translation: which differs from faithful translation only in as far as it must take more account of the aesthetic value of the source language text.

□ Adaptation: which is the freest form of translation, and is used mainly for plays and poetry; the themes, characters, plots are usually preserved, the source language culture is converted to the target language culture and the text is rewritten. Hatim (2001) has described adaptation as the adjustment where strategies including addition, omission, and cultural substitution are used.] These are used to enhance the acceptability of the target text in that it makes the intended meaning more easily comprehensible to the audience. Guidère (2006) has examined a large sample of advertisements translated into English, Spanish, Portuguese, and Arabic, observing that translators use adaptation for a number of certain functions. First, translators adapt the source language to accommodate cultural differences. Guidère (2006) suggests that translators should pay attention to the social and cultural aspects of the target market ranging from religion, to social habits, to rules of conduct, to ethical norms. The second function for which translators of advertisements, in general, and travel brochures, in particular, use adaptation in dealing with technical terms by substituting technical terms with easier words that make messages clearer and more understandable to the target audience. The third function of adaptation is that it enables translators to add words that add to the promotional value of the product. Undoubtedly, using this strategy provides translators with a certain degree of freedom by which they can apply their cultural knowledge and linguistic abilities using addition and omission.

□ Free translation: it produces the target language text without the style, form, or content of the original. Omission is defined as dropping a word or words from the source language text in translation (Iacovoni, 2009) which can be the outcome of cultural clashes between the source text and the target text. Due to such clashes, the translator omits words that do not have equivalents in the target language or that may not seem natural to the target audience. According to Fraiwan (2007), omission is justified on the grounds that it is used to delete words that may hinder the acceptability of the target text to the target audience. Otherwise, omission is the result of translator's carelessness, lack of attention, and ignorance, which is not justifiable. Such carelessness or ignorance may lead to deleting necessary words that are essential to persuading the readers to choose the advertised tour. Translators may also make use of the strategy of addition allows the translator to add certain words that may help satisfy the target audience. According to Newmark (1988), translators may have to add additional information that can be cultural, technical or linguistic. Addition is utilized to serve purposes such as emphasizing a specific function of the tour, promoting a tour, highlighting the main effect of the advertised tour, helping customers identify the type of the tour they intend to choose, or for linguistic purposes.

Smith (2006) defines transference as untranslated retention of the original in that the transferred words in the source text are exactly copied to the target text. Transliteration and

transference as two translation strategies may not always meet the expectations of a given audience, and since literal translation may not be appropriate to be used in an advertising text, translators may opt for the strategy of adaptation which is addressed in the following section.

- Naturalization: it adapts the SL word first to the normal pronunciation, then to the normal morphology of the TL (Newmark, 1988, p.82)
- Cultural equivalent: it means replacing a cultural word in the SL with a TL one. however, they are not accurate (Newmark, 1988, p.83)
- Functional equivalent: it requires the use of a culture-neutral word. (Newmark, 1988, p.83)
- Descriptive equivalent: in this procedure the meaning of the culture-specific word is explained in several words (Newmark, 1988, p.83).
- Componential analysis: it means "comparing an SL word with a TL word which has a similar meaning but is not an obvious one-to-one equivalent, by demonstrating first their common and then their differing sense components." (Newmark, 1988, p.114)
- Synonymy: it is a "near TL equivalent." Here economy trumps accuracy. (Newmark, 1988,p.84)
- Through-translation: it is the literal translation of common collocations, names of organizations and components of compounds. It can also be called: calque or loan translation. (Newmark, 1988, p.84)
- Shifts or transpositions: it involves a change in the grammar from SL to TL, for instance, (i) change from singular to plural, (ii) the change required when a specific SL structure does not exist in the TL, (iii) change of an SL verb to a TL word, change of an SL noun group to a TL noun and so forth. (Newmark, 1988, p.86)
- Modulation: it occurs when the translator reproduces the message of the original text in the TL text in conformity with the current norms of the TL, since the SL and the TL may appear dissimilar in terms of perspective. (Newmark, 1988, p.88)
- Recognized translation: it occurs when the translator normally uses the official or the generally accepted translation of any institutional term. (Newmark, 1988, p. 89)
- Compensation: it occurs when loss of meaning in one part of a sentence is compensated in another part. (Newmark, 1988, p.90)
- Paraphrase: in this procedure the meaning of the culture-specific word is explained. Here the explanation is much more detailed than that of descriptive equivalent. (Newmark, 1988, p.91)
- Couplets: it occurs when the translator combines two different procedures. (Newmark, 1988,p.91)
- Notes: notes are additional information in a translation. (Newmark, 1988, p.91).

Having studied the terminology of Uzbek tourism lexically-semantically, once again we note that a large part of it is formed from foreign (literally from English terminology) in the means of word acquisition. After all, there is no absolutely pure language itself, without foreign words. During the course of historical development, the words of other ethnic groups were adopted by people, sometimes voluntarily, sometimes under certain pressure, as a result of economic, political and cultural ties of different nations and nationalities of different scales. Particularly, during our study, we will focus more on linguistic phenomena associated with

the process of learning. In some cases, if the Uzbek tourist terminology is directly translated into literary criticism: international scientific-practical conference on modern approaches and perspectives foreign terms, in many cases it is necessary to fall into the process of "uzbekization", which requires deeper observation. The mastering of terms in which structural components are dominant, the meaning of one meaning or another (base) is evident, is carried out directly by translation. For example, departure card (кетиш/жўнаш варақаси), arrival card (келиш варақаси), agency agreement (агентлик шартномаси), airport terminal (аэропорт терминали), farm tourism (ферма туризми), agency coupon (агентлик купони), alternate airport (муқобил аэропорт), air carrier (ҳаво ташувчиси), baggage tag (юк/багаж ёрлиғи), excess baggage (ортиқча юк), dome car (гумбазли автоулов), connecting flight (уловчи парвоз), one-way ticket (бир томонлама чипта), direct selling (бевосита сотув/савдо), e-ticket (электрон чипта), duplicate reservation (дубликат буюртма), industrial tourism (индустриал/саноат туризми), Hajj Pilgrimage (Ҳаж зиёрати), mass tourism (оммавий туризм), seasonality (мавсумийлик), transit traveler (транзит сайёҳ/йўловчи), aquatic sports (сув спорти), cultural heritage (маданий меърос), field sports (дала спорти), hotel tariff (меҳмонхона тарифи).

When deriving the baggage room, auto rental lexemes, we can observe that in the Uzbek language they have become a single-component word with two components (юкхона, автоижара). The terms cafeteria, Business Class, duty-free, ecotourism, agritourism, ethnic tourism, business center, festival, catering, force majeure are "uzbekintegrated" with slight orthographic changes.

In order to remove the outlandish color from the terms couchette, diversification, brochure, theme park, sanatorium, planetarium their core is preserved and changed to an additional front plan:

Couchette → ixcham yotoq

Brochure → broshyura

Theme park → tematik park

Sanatorium → sanatoriya

Planetarium → planetariy

In the process of integrating these words, the influence of the fraternal Russian language is evident. Subsequently, the lexemes affixation, which has acquired a new appearance, has a Russian character. Seaplane, flying boat terms itself presented themselves in the innovations in the development of transport, representing a concept whose structural components consist of a hybrid combination of different types of transport (that is, in the form of dengiz samalyoti, uchar qayiq). There are even more hybrid compounds in the English tourist terminology. For example, in the form of fly cruise, fly drive, fly rail.

In conclusion, when translating tourism terms into uzbek we should investigate deeply the translation theory and use the most suitable strategies and find most suitable equivalent to achieve main goal of translation. 1) the terminology of English Tourism was formed on the basis of the influence of many cultures; 2) the synonyms, antonyms, polysemes and the figurative meaning in the terminology of English tourism were at a significant level; 3) the majority of the terminology of Uzbek tourism came from abroad, in particular, through the development of Vocabulary from the English language; 4) the Uzbek culture has enriched the

world dictionary with terms related to many areas, especially connected with oriental architecture.

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